

1 First trial of a prototype chain-flail delimber for the European short rotation poplar plantations

2
3 Raffaele Spinelli^{1,2,3}, Barnabas Kovacs⁴, Patrik Heger⁴, David Heilig⁵, Natascia Magagnotti^{1,2,3}.

4
5
6 ¹Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche – Istituto per la Bioeconomia (CNR IBE), Firenze, ITALY

7 ² Australian Forest Operations Research Alliance - University of the Sunshine Coast (AFORA USC),
8 Maroochydore DC, Queensland, AUSTRALIA

9 ³ Forestry Research Institute of Sweden (SKOGFORSK), Uppsala, SWEDEN

10 ⁴ IKEA Industry Slovakia, Malacky, SLOVAKIA

11 ⁵ University of Sopron – Institute of Earth and Environmental Sciences, Sopron, HUNGARY

12 13 14 15 **Abstract**

16 Small tree size represents a main challenge for single-tree handling techniques and caps harvesting
17 productivity in short rotation poplar (SRP) plantations. That challenge is best met by a shift towards
18 mass-handling. Chain flail delimiting is one of the best solutions for multi-tree processing, but
19 commercially available equipment is often too heavy and expensive for European operations.
20 Therefore, an Italian company developed a compact chain flail delimber-debarker (CFDD)
21 specifically designed for small-scale SRP. The machine was tested in Western Slovakia in early March
22 2022. The test included a five-days endurance trial and a controlled experiment on 16 carefully
23 measured wood piles representing “strong” and “weak” trees, i.e. trees with a mean diameter at
24 breast height (DBH) of 12 and 10 cm, respectively. The endurance trial was quite successful since no
25 mechanical problems were recorded during the five-days period. Delimiting and crosscutting quality
26 were as good as those obtained with a standard processor head, while log yield was generally better,
27 averaging 42% and 68% for the “weak” and the “strong” trees, respectively. Productivity was on a
28 par with the alternative cut-to-length technology options and can be significantly increased once
29 the prototype will be further developed. In general, the new compact CFDD may become the best
30 option for handling the small trees offered by underdeveloped SRP plantations, which cannot be
31 efficiently harvested with the cut-to-length system.

32
33 **Keywords:** Harvesting; Logging; Equipment; Operations; Productivity; Efficiency

34 35 36 37 **Introduction**

38
39 Chain flail delimber debarkers (CFDDs) are multi-stem processing machines that use fastly rotating
40 chain links to remove branches and bark off cut trees (Watson et al. 1993). However crude, these
41 machines are fast and effective, and their relative simplicity results in good reliability: after all, once
42 the machine components are correctly dimensioned, there is very little that can fail. Simplicity and
43 reliability are neither the only assets of CFDD equipment, nor the main ones. In fact, the most
44 important benefit offered by CFDD technology is the capacity to easily handle more trees per cycle.
45 Depending on machine type, tree size and expected work quality, a CFDD can efficiently process 3
46 to 7 trees at a time, which boosts productivity and represents a great advantage especially when
47 handling small trees (Thompson and Sturos 1991). Through mass-handling, CFDDs can offset the
48 productivity handicap imposed by small trees (Nakagawa et al 2007): as tree size gets smaller, more

49 trees are gathered into the same load and throughflow is stabilized (Mooney et al. 2000). Their
50 ability to buffer tree size effects is best demonstrated by the failure of all CFDD productivity studies
51 to estimate a strong relationship between productivity and stem volume, given that the strongest
52 models yet produced have a coefficient of determination R^2 around 0.30 (McEwan et al. 2019,
53 Hartsough et al. 2002, Ghaffariyan et al 2013). Furthermore, the delimiting principle adopted by
54 chainflail machines does not rely on a knife sliding along the stem surface and its efficiency is less
55 dependent on stem form (Labelle et al. 2016), so that a chainflail can turn into a usable product
56 even those tree portions that are too small or too malformed for recovering with any other
57 processing systems (Buggie 1997, Spinelli et al. 2020a). For that reason, CFDD technology is
58 especially popular when dealing with small trees, as normally obtained from short-rotation
59 industrial plantations designed to produce high-quality fiber for manufacturing pulpwood or other
60 high-end commodities, rather than low-grade biomass (Spinelli and Hartsough 2006). An ideal field
61 of application for this technology is represented by the new medium-rotation tree farms,
62 established in Europe on agricultural land and designed for producing a mix of timber and biomass
63 (Freer-Smith et al. 2019). There are currently at least 20 000 hectares of these plantations in Europe
64 – especially in the Eastern regions (IPP 2019, Werner et al. 2012). Most of these plantations have
65 been established quite recently and large scale harvesting has just started, so that both plantations
66 managers and harvesting service providers are still searching for the best solutions to efficient
67 harvesting (McEwan et al. 2020). One common challenge they all face is small tree size, which makes
68 the mass-handling capability of CFDD equipment especially attractive. However, CFDD
69 manufacturers are all concentrated in North America and they cater mainly for the Americas and
70 Australia: they have not developed the European market, which held a much lower potential at the
71 time when CFDD technology expanded (Raymond and Franklin 1990, Stokes and Watson 1991).

72
73 In fact, the European forest industry has shown some interest for CFDD technology, but its focus
74 has been on early thinning operations, where low profitability prevents the major investment
75 required by industrial operations (Kofman 2022). Over time, smaller-scale CFDD units have been
76 developed within the scope of various R&D projects, especially in the Nordic regions (Alakangas
77 1995). Although short-lived, those experiences witness to a sustained interest in developing CFDD
78 technology, and to a fundamental conviction of its large potential. Unfortunately, the focus on early
79 thinning has condemned all those attempts to failure, given that early thinning – not CFDD
80 development – is a problem that has found no satisfactory solution until now.

81
82 So, when the new tree farms are finally offering a much more promising field of application to CFDD
83 equipment, no such equipment is available – except for one lonely American CFDD that has worked
84 for many years in an Italian logyard and now awaits scrapping in Portugal! Unable to obtain a test
85 unit from the American manufactures, plantation managers have eventually supported the
86 development of yet another European prototype, hopefully more successful than the previous ones.
87 In 2021, Biomass Work Ltd. and Piacentini Metalworks joined forces to develop the initial prototype
88 of a small-scale CFDD. Both companies are located in Lombardy, northern Italy, where chainflailing
89 has been practiced for decades as a way to clean rootstock after extraction from clearcut poplar
90 plantations (Spinelli et al. 2005). Hence the familiarity of many Lombard companies with flailing
91 technology and the availability of retired root-cleaning equipment, which was eventually tapped for
92 components. The prototype was built at the end of 2021 and successfully tested in February 2022.
93 Therefore, the goal of this paper is to describe the machine and present the results of its first
94 working trials in terms of productivity (tons per hour), log yield (% log mass over total mass) and
95 general reliability (frequency and duration of mechanical downtime events). Since the productivity
96 of any machine is generally affected by piece size, the prototype was tested on two different

97 feedstock types: “strong” and “weak” trees. Of course, that definition was relative to the type of
98 plantation at hand, which generally offers small trees, only. In the case of this study, “strong” trees
99 had a mean diameter at breast height (DBH) in the range of 12 cm, “weak” in the range of 10 cm.
100 While apparently small, that difference has a significant impact on the performance of single-tree
101 equipment and plays a crucial role in the profitability of short rotation poplar plantations (Spinelli
102 et al. 2022a).

103

104 **Materials and methods**

105

106 The chainflail prototype was a built from a pre-existing root cleaner, consisting of a box-like
107 structure supporting two rotating drums. The drums were mounted 1 m apart and were powered
108 by two variable displacement hydraulic motors that would turn at 800-1000 rpm, depending on the
109 rotational regime of the endothermic engine that fed them. Each drum carried 16 flails, consisting
110 of 6 hardened chain links each. Normally, the device would be fed vertically from the top, so that
111 the short rootstocks to be cleaned would dangle between the two drums and would be flailed until
112 all the dirt was removed. Therefore, the first step in prototype development consisted in turning
113 the device by 90° to enable horizontal feeding. Then, an infeed table was added, for supporting
114 incoming tree bunches. At the other end of the flail, a metal chute was installed for holding that
115 stem portion that had passed through the flail (Figure 1). Two bump plates were added: one in front
116 of the infeed table and the other at the end of the chute, for indexing tree butts and assuring
117 accurate crosscutting of the whole bunch. Since the target log length was 4 m, the second bump
118 plate – that at the end of the chute – was placed at 4 m from the centerline of the flail drums, so
119 that the delimbed stem portion would extend to exactly 4 m and would be clearly visible at
120 crosscutting. While the eventual commercial product would be fitted with its own hydraulic pump
121 and power pack, this first prototype was designed for connecting to the hydraulic system of its
122 transport, due to budget restrictions. All was mounted on a roll-on roll-off flat deck skip for easy
123 transportation between sites: the total weight of the chainflail device was 3 t, including the skip that
124 weighed 1 t itself. The whole operation was contained in a 6-axle truck-and-trailer rig, whereby the
125 CFDD skip was loaded on the three-axle truck and the excavator tasked to feed it sat on the three-
126 axle trailer. The excavator was a tracked 13-t model, fitted with a grapple saw. The typical work
127 cycle consisted of the following tasks: picking a bunch of trees off the pile with the excavator;
128 pushing the bunch through the chainflail and back, until satisfactory delimiting would be achieved;
129 placing the bunch on the ground and re-grabbing it at 4 m from the butt; crosscutting it at the 4 m
130 length; repeating the operation if a second 4-m long log could be obtained; finally, stacking the logs
131 and the tops onto their respective piles (Figure 2). One operator was enough to relocate and operate
132 the whole system.

133

134 After a brief test run near the workshop in Italy, the machine was moved to Western Slovakia and
135 tested on one of the short-rotation poplar plantations managed by IKEA Industry near Malacky, in
136 close proximity of a major particle board factory tasked with producing a highly innovative poplar
137 based lightweight panel. In particular, the test plantation was located near Gajary (48° 29' 10.87" N;
138 16° 55' 25.52" in WGS84), in the Morava river floodplain. Local climate was described as “warm
139 temperate, fully humid, with hot summer climate” (Cfb) according to the Köppen-Geiger
140 classification (Rubel et al 2017). The mean annual temperature was 11 °C in the 2014-2020 interval
141 and the average annual precipitation was 742 mm. Soil was a Mollic Gleysol, with sandy texture and
142 groundwater levels between 1.5 and 2.0 m from the surface. The test was conducted in early March
143 2022. Weather during the test was consistently warm and dry, with occasional light precipitation.
144 Air temperature varied between -2 and +14 C°. The plantation was a 6-year-old poplar stand

145 established at a square spacing of 3.0 m x 2.0 m with hybrid poplar (*Populus x euramericana* Dode
146 (Guinier)), clone 'AF18'(Heilig et al. 2021, Landgraf et al. 2020, Meyer et al. 2021).

147

148 The test machine was operated by the owner of Biomass Work Ltd., who was a qualified forestry
149 professional with many years of experience in poplar harvesting work. He had also operated the
150 chainflail for many years, although only in the rootstock cleaning configuration, given the absolute
151 novelty of the new machine derived from it (Figure 3). Nevertheless, he was quite familiar with the
152 working principle, the expected results and the hazards of chainflail operation. Before starting the
153 study proper, the operator worked half a day on an unmarked stack in order to perfect his routine
154 and iron out possible difficulties. After that, the experiment proper commenced. The machine was
155 run continuously for 5 work shifts and during that time all mechanical downtime would be recorded,
156 together with its cause. That general trial was integrated with a time and motion study conducted
157 over two different feedstock types: standard trees and underdeveloped trees - respectively the
158 "strong" and the "weak" tree treatments. The former would normally yield at least one 4-m log -
159 more often two; the latter would only yield one 4-m log, if any at all.

160

161 The experimental design was a factorial scheme where each treatment was repeated 8 times. Each
162 repetition consisted of one pile of approximately 130 trees, in order to reflect the same batch size
163 adopted in other similar studies conducted under the same research programme – thus achieving
164 comparability, in case of further use of the same datasets. The chainflail would process the piles in
165 a random order, to neutralize any potential background noise derived from machine wear or
166 operator fatigue. To minimize the latter effect, at the end of each pile the study was halted to allow
167 for the operator to rest, while the support team cleaned and inspected the machine for any signs of
168 malfunction (e.g. leaks, accelerated wear etc.). Taking a brief rest pause every hour of work is a
169 recommended practice in commercial operations, too.

170

171 The selected test metrics were: productivity (mass output/time input), log yield (log mass/total
172 mass) and mechanical reliability (frequency and duration of mechanical downtime over the total
173 test time). Therefore, we measured: tree size, product mass (separately for logs and biomass), time
174 input, frequency and duration of any mechanical stops.

175

176 The circumference at breast height of all trees in all piles was measured manually with a measuring
177 tape and then converted into diameter at breast height (DBH), over bark. Furthermore, 6 trees
178 covering the whole DBH distribution were destructively sampled in order to determine their total
179 height and weight, separately for the theoretical log and chip portions (Krejza et al. 2017; Urban et
180 al. 2015). Destructive sampling allowed estimating the relationship between DBH, total height and
181 mass, which was used to predict the mass packed into each individual pile (Headlee and Zalesny
182 2019). Previous studies have shown that it is possible to build reliable allometric functions with such
183 a small sample, when tree variability is as small as found in even-aged clonal poplar (Hartmann 2010;
184 Hjelm 2015; Verlinden et al. 2013). Initial mass estimates were later adjusted using ad-hoc
185 correction factors obtained by matching the estimated log and biomass yields with the actual
186 amounts taken to the factory weighbridge. That was done separately for the log and for the chip
187 portion obtained from each of the two treatments, in order to account for variations in log recovery
188 that might be associated with the treatments (i.e. 4 correction factors). Moisture content was
189 determined both at the time of destructive sampling and at the time of delivery to the factory, so
190 as to match dry mass estimates with dry mass weighbridge data. In both cases, moisture content
191 was determined with the gravimetric method, according to EN ISO 18134-2:2015. Mean moisture
192 content at delivery was 55% (standard deviation = 2.7%). Depending on treatment, the ratio

193 between factory dry mass and inventory dry mass varied from 0.75 to 1.12 with an overall average
194 at 0.85 - meaning that the field inventory overestimated actual harvest by about 15%.

195
196 Delimiting quality was visually assessed by the factory production managers who attended the trials.
197 Log length was regularly checked with a tape measure all along the duration of the trials. The
198 machine was set for delimiting, not debarking.

199
200 During the test, researchers determined the time taken by the CFDD to process each individual pile,
201 using a stopwatch accurate to the second. Both productive time and delay time were recorded
202 (Bjorheden et al. 1995), but the latter was excluded from the study, where it was replaced by a 20%
203 delay factor. That was done because the time spent on each pile was too short (about 1 hour) to
204 accurately estimate delay time. The 20% increase applied to the data was consistent with the
205 findings of previous published studies, with special reference to the harvesting of plantation forestry
206 (Spinelli and Visser 2008). That figure was also quite close to the sum of all delays recorded during
207 the complete study, as conducted on the 16 piles.

208
209 The pile-level time study was accompanied by a parallel cycle-level elemental time study
210 (Magagnotti et al. 2011). That would cover more than half of chainflail cycles on each pile, where
211 cycles were identified as the time to complete the processing of a tree bunch broken off the pile
212 and fed to the chainflail. The total cycle then included all tasks required for turning a group of trees
213 from the test pile into logs and biomass stacked onto their respective piles. The goal of this study
214 component was to determine if treatment would specifically impact one or more work steps within
215 the complete flailing task. Furthermore, the elemental time study would indicate which ones are
216 the most time-consuming work steps and address future improvements of the prototype. This study
217 split the complete cycle into the following work tasks (elements):

218
219 Grab = Time spent grabbing a tree bunch and indexing the trees against the bump plate. It ends
220 when the bunch is inserted between the rotating flails (easily identified through the flail-on-wood
221 noise). The record includes a count of trees in the bunch;

222
223 Process = Time spent delimiting the bunch and crosscutting it. It ends when the last log obtained
224 from the bunch is crosscut. The record includes a count of the logs produced from the original
225 bunch;

226
227 Stack logs = Time spent moving the crosscut logs onto the log stack;

228
229 Pile residues = Time spent moving the residues (tops and branches) onto the biomass pile;

230
231 Other work time = any other work time – typically clearing debris from under the infeed opening
232 and chute etc.

233
234 The pile-level study data was used to quantify operation productivity and log yield (dependent
235 variables) as average values, and the differences between alternative treatments (independent
236 variables) was checked using non-parametric statistics as a safeguard against possible violations of
237 the parametric assumptions. Given the only two treatments were being compared (“weak” vs.
238 “strong”), a non-parametric test would not be much less informative than a standard parametric
239 test, while being more robust – hence more reliable. In particular, the Mann-Whitney unpaired
240 comparison test was used for this study. Since we renounced the normality assumption, centrality

241 was represented through Medians – not Means. For all analyses, the significance level was set at
242 $\alpha < 0.05$. The analyses were implemented with the software Minitab 17, one of the most popular
243 statistical software in the field of engineering (Okagbue et al. 2021)

244

245 **Results**

246 The trials lasted 5 full work days, so that one could get an overall impression of machine reliability
247 and endurance. No mechanical failures were recorded during those five shifts. Within that period,
248 the time study occupied 2 days, during which the machine processed 52 bone dry tons (BDT) of
249 wood – i.e. the 16 test piles..

250

251 Delimiting quality was considered satisfactory by the factory production managers on site and at
252 the receiving facility. In fact, visual inspection of the log piles showed that delimiting quality and
253 surface damage were not much different from those offered by the cut-to-length processor that
254 worked alongside the CFDD on the same landing (Figure 4). Cutting length accuracy was also
255 comparable and generally satisfactory (overlength = 2 to 10 cm).

256

257 By design, piles with “strong” trees had been sourced from higher-yielding areas of the plantation
258 (48 BDT ha^{-1} vs. 37 BDT ha^{-1}): they were significantly larger (3.7 vs. 2.7 BDT), as they contained more
259 and larger trees (better survival and growth). In particular, median DBH was 14% larger (12.4 cm vs.
260 10.9 cm) and tree mass 20% higher (28 vs 23 kg dry matter) for the trees in the “strong” piles (Table
261 1). That was part of the plan and the data confirmed that part succeeded, at least.

262

263 Chainflail productivity ranged between 2.5 and 4.7 BDT SMH^{-1} : it was 40% higher for the “weak”
264 treatment compared with the “strong” one, and the difference was statistically significant (Table 2).
265 In contrast, log yield was significantly higher for the “strong” treatment, with 69 percent points or
266 a 40% increment over the “weak” treatment that plateaued at 42 percent points.

267

268 The elemental cycle-level time study confirmed the results of the pile-level study and showed the
269 mechanisms regulating productivity (Table 3). In particular, it offered a direct witness to the mass-
270 handling capacity of the chainflail and of the associated benefits. Under the “weak” treatment, more
271 trees (6.4 vs. 4.9) were processed in each cycle. The maximum was 8 trees per cycle on a pile
272 average, but the maximum for an individual cycle could reach or exceed 10 trees. The number of
273 logs per tree was obviously lower for the “weak” treatment compared with the “strong” one, since
274 trees in the latter group would normally offer two 4 m logs per stem, instead of one. For that reason,
275 cycle time was 20% lower for the “weak” treatment.

276

277 As a matter of fact, manufacturing a second log from the same tree was rather cumbersome. After
278 crosscutting the first set of logs from the butt section, the whole processing sequence had to be
279 repeated. The bunch had to be indexed again, fed into the chainflail and pulled out; the second set
280 of logs was crosscut and finally the logs and the biomass were moved to their respective piles.

281

282 The combined effect of a shorter cycle time and a larger number of trees per cycle caused a dramatic
283 increase of tree-based productivity under the “weak” treatment, when the chainflail was able to
284 process over 200 trees per hour. Mass handling allowed offsetting the tree size handicap, which is
285 what multi-tree machines are designed for.

286

287 A more detailed analysis of the main work elements indicated that processing (i.e. delimiting and
288 crosscutting) was the largest contributor to cycle time, accounting for approximately half of the total

289 time consumption regardless of treatment (Figure 5). Log stacking and residue piling took twice as
290 much time per cycle under the “strong” treatment than under the “weak” one (18 s vs. 9 s and 14 s
291 vs. 7 s, respectively). That difference was statistically significant and is likely due to the larger mass
292 per cycle handled under the “strong” treatment. In contrast, grabbing and indexing the trees before
293 processing took about the same time per cycle, regardless of treatment. In absolute terms, cycles
294 were longer under the “strong” treatment simply because more mass was handled per cycle.
295 Besides, the current machine design was not ideal for repeated crosscutting, as was described just
296 above.

297

298 **Discussion**

299

300 Like most studies, this one has its own limitations that must be addressed before endeavouring into
301 any meaningful discussion, so that readers can judge for themselves how reliable is the information
302 contained in this manuscript and how it could be transferred to their own work environment. The
303 first and obvious limitation is the prototypal character of the equipment on test. For that reason, all
304 results must be interpreted with much caution, and especially those that concern operational
305 productivity. The machine can and will be improved. In particular, the cumbersome processing
306 sequence must be streamlined: in any efficient conversion process, the raw material must come in
307 from one end and the processed product must fall out from the other end. The current in-and-out
308 work sequence is inefficient and requires iterative indexing of the tree bunch, which is a time-
309 consuming operation.

310

311 The second limitation is the collective analysis of the cycle-level data at the pile level. That is, the
312 data that were collected on a cycle basis were later grouped by pile and the average element and
313 cycle time were extracted. Therefore, the cycle-level study results were not reported at the cycle-
314 level. That finds its justification in the specific work routine of the CFDD in its current configuration.
315 The in-and-out work mode implied that the second batch of logs from trees in one cycle would often
316 be processed together with the first batch of logs from trees in the next cycle, so as to have the
317 stronger logs supporting the weaker ones for minimum breakage. Similarly, the logs and the biomass
318 would be piled intermittently and only when their quantity were large enough to hinder further
319 work, not regularly with its cycle. Therefore, frequent non-cyclic activities made it very difficult to
320 keep cycles exactly separated, justifying collective data analysis (Punnett and Wegman, 2004).

321

322 The third limitation of this study is the usual concern about operator selection: testing just one
323 operator makes one wonder how much the data obtained from this study can be generalized
324 (Leonello et al. 2012). The question is compounded by the fact that the machine is a first prototype
325 and therefore no operator – not even our test operator – could possibly achieve any significant
326 experience with its operation. True, the operator selected for the test had long-term experience of
327 flailing rootstocks in vertically-fed rootstock cleaners, but flailing 1-m long taproots in a vertical tub
328 is not the same as flailing 14-m long trees in a horizontal device. All the above strongly suggests that
329 the productivity data must be taken with much caution, as they are likely to change quite
330 dramatically once the machine has received the necessary improvements and the operator has
331 gained more experience with its use.

332

333 As of now, it is difficult to make any solid projections about the future long-term productivity of an
334 improved version of the compact CFDD presented in this study. However, it is unlikely that a
335 streamlining of the material flow through the machine could significantly affect log stacking and
336 residue piling, which are virtually independent of CFDD design. The main benefits of the new design

337 would be accrued at the processing stage, which accounts for roughly half of the total cycle time.
338 Therefore, if the improvements could decrease processing time to ½ or 1/3 of the actual duration
339 recorded in this study, overall cycle time would drop by 25% or 33%, respectively. Since a stronger
340 effect would be expected on the “strong” trees compared with the “weak” ones, the hypothetical
341 productivity would increase to 3.8 BDT SMH⁻¹ (i.e. 2.9 * 1.33) and 5.2 BDT SMH⁻¹ (i.e. 4.1 * 1.25),
342 respectively. For the measured moisture content of 55% and after rounding, those figures would
343 amount to approximately 9 and 12 green tons (gt) SMH⁻¹, respectively. That is still much below the
344 productivity reported for commercial CFDD models deployed on SRF poplar and eucalypt tree farms
345 (Table 4). Those machines are at least 4 times more productive than the prototype presented here,
346 even after its eventual upgrading. On the other hand, they are much heavier, more powerful and
347 expensive than our prototype. A base CFDD unit like – for instance – the Peterson Pacific 4810F
348 weighs over 20 t, is powered by a 260 kW engine and sells at over 500,000 USD (Cordes 2020): so
349 definitely another league. In fact, the small prototype flail developed as part of this research has
350 neither the potential nor the intention to compete for the same market sector against the larger
351 and more mature Northamerican products. The idea is rather to find a solution for those many
352 European entrepreneurs who will never be able to purchase such a machine, nor to find large
353 enough tracts for its successful deployment. If one must be found, the main competitor is rather the
354 roadside processor, which the new CFDD could try to replace whenever tree size was too small for
355 effective single-tree operation.

356
357 The work quality assessment presented in this report is much more robust compared with the
358 productivity assessment. There is no reason to expect a dramatic improvement in that department,
359 nor any need for it: length accuracy, delimiting quality and log recovery rate are already quite good,
360 although minor improvements can and will be achieved in the future. In particular, log recovery rate
361 (i.e. log yield) is better than recorded for all the other tests conducted with the alternative
362 technologies on the same feedstock type. Table 5 reports the tree characteristics and the log yield
363 results obtained from other similar trials conducted by the same team, with the same methods and
364 for the same log yield specifications: 4 m log-length and 7 (or 8) cm small end diameter. Those trials
365 were conducted with a variety of different equipment, such as harvesters, processors and grapple
366 saws. Since the different figures originated from different datasets collected within distinct trials,
367 we did not attempt a direct statistical comparison with the results of this study: that has been
368 planned for another study and is already in progress. However, the table indicates that the log yield
369 recorded for the prototype CFDD is already at least as good as the best figures obtained with the
370 previous trials of the alternative technologies. What is most interesting, the edge gained by the
371 CFDD is especially large for the smallest trees (DBH<12 cm), which qualifies the new machine as
372 especially suited for low-yield plantations (Buggie 1997).

373
374 Visual observation of the work process suggested that the better log yield recorded for the CFDD
375 was due to the tested CTL heads inflicting excessive damage to the processed stems, especially the
376 smallest ones. That seems to contradict the high level of stem damage generally associated with
377 CFDD operation (Favreau 1997). In fact, that association is generally made for machines used for
378 combined delimiting and debarking – not just delimiting (Chahal A, Ciolkosz D. 2019). Obviously, flail
379 action must be much more energetic for thoroughly peeling the stem surface, rather than just
380 knocking off the few scattered (and often dry) branches that one may find on the basal portion of a
381 young poplar stem grown in dense plantation. In fact, those branches are generally so light and
382 scarce that the WTH trials n° 8 and 10 in Table 5 adopted a simple grapple saw to process the trees,
383 on the assumption that most limbs would be crashed during handling (Spinelli et al. 2019). However,
384 delimiting quality was not deemed satisfactory in those two cases, and the relatively high log yield

385 figures associated with them should be significantly reduced due to high factory rejection rates. For
386 that reason, post-processing motor-manual trimming of surviving branches and branch stubs was
387 introduced with trial n° 9, but that solution lacked long-term financial and social sustainability:
388 hence the idea of introducing a CFDD.

389
390 While the machine in this study was used for delimiting only, it can certainly be set for integrated
391 delimiting and debarking, if the need arises. To that end, one could simply extend the permanence
392 of the stems under the flail, change the flail rotation speed or replace the chains with a more
393 aggressive type (Spinelli et al. 2020a). However, such adjustments would likely decrease
394 productivity and log yield, so they should be pursued only if necessary (Hartsough et al. 2000).
395 Nevertheless, easy switching to the debarking mode may further expand the CFDD's potential and
396 make it appealing to the many stakeholders who are trying to reintroduce in-field debarking to
397 European forest operation in an attempt to mitigate insect outbreaks and/or soil nutrient removal
398 (Heppelman et al. 2019, Holzleitner and Kanzian 2022, Mergl et al. 2021).

399
400 In any case, the machine is still quite new and it can be significantly improved and expanded, both
401 as a pure delimiting and as an integrated delimiting-debarker. Further studies will guide improvement
402 and allow defining the optimum configurations and settings for each job and tree type.

403

404

405 **Conclusions**

406 Even as an early prototype, the compact CFDD presented in this study offered a very good
407 performance. Productivity and product quality were on a par with alternative and more mature CTL
408 technology options currently applied to those stands, while value recovery was generally better.
409 Reliability was exceptionally good for a prototype, since no mechanical problems were recorded
410 during the five-days endurance test. The machine works best with the smallest trees, which are a
411 challenge for all other options. Compared with the industrial CFDD already available on the market,
412 the machine on test is much smaller, lighter and less expensive. While not as productive, it is
413 definitely more affordable for European contractors and can be deployed on small-scale operations.
414 Due to its compact size, it could also be installed on a forwarder and operated at the stump-site
415 wherever soil fertility concerns make it preferable to leave branches and bark inside the stand.
416 Further improvements are planned and they may greatly increase the efficiency of the new machine.

417

418 **Funding declaration:** H2020 Excellent Science, 745874 – BBI JU Dendromass for Europe (D4EU)

419

420 **Author contribution statement:** All authors contributed to the conceptualization of the study;
421 methodology: Raffaele Spinelli, David Heilig and Natascia Magagnotti; formal analysis: Raffaele
422 Spinelli, David Heilig and Natascia Magagnotti; resources: Raffaele Spinelli and Barnabas Kovac;
423 operational supervision and management: Patrik Heger; original draft preparation: Raffaele
424 Spinelli and Natascia Magagnotti; review and editing all Authors.

425

426 **Conflict of interest:** The Authors declare no conflict of interest

427

428 **References**

429

430 Alakangas E (1995) Demonstration Project of the Bioenergy Research Programme Started. *Energia*
431 10 (5): 30-31. VTT Energy, Jyväskylä, Finland.

432

433 Björheden R, Apel K, Shiba M, Thompson M (1995) IUFRO Forest work study nomenclature. Swedish
434 University of Agricultural Science, Dept. of Operational Efficiency, Garpenberg. 16 p.
435

436 Buggie WJ (1991) Flail chippers can improve fibre utilization in small softwoods. Canadian Forest
437 Industries Magazine, August/September, 28–31.
438

439 Chahal A, Ciolkosz D (2019) A review of wood-bark adhesion: methods and mechanics of debarking
440 for woody biomass. Wood and Fiber Science 51 (3): 1-12.
441

442 Cordes C (2020) Personal communication, E-mail on December 2nd, 2020 @ 11:49. Astec Industries,
443 Eugene, OR, USA.
444

445 Favreau J (1997) A comparison of fibre loss during full-tree and cut-to-length harvesting. Technical
446 Report 118. Forest Engineering Research Institute of Canada, Pointe-Claire, Quebec. 10 p.
447

448 Freer-Smith P, Muys B, Bozzano M, Drössler L, Farrelly N, Jactel H, Korhonen J, Minotta G, Nijnik M,
449 Orazio C (2019) Plantation forests in Europe: challenges and opportunities. From Science to Policy
450 9. European Forest Institute. <https://doi.org/10.36333/fs09>
451

452 Ghaffariyan M, Brown M, Spinelli R (2013) Evaluating efficiency, chip quality and harvesting residues
453 of a chipping operation with flail and chipper in Western Australia. Croat J For Eng 34: 189-199.
454

455 Hartmann KU (2010) Entwicklung eines Ertragschätzers für Kurzumtriebsbestände aus Pappel. PhD
456 Thesis, Technische Universität Dresden, Fakultät Forst-, Geo- und Hydrowissenschaften. Tharandt,
457 Germany. 162 p.
458

459 Hartsough B, Spinelli R, Pottle S, Klepac J (2000) Fiber recovery with chain flail delimiting/debarking
460 and chipping of hybrid poplar. Int J For Eng 11: 59-65.
461

462 Hartsough B, Spinelli R, Pottle S (2002) Delimiting hybrid poplar prior to processing with a
463 flail/chipper. For Prod J 52: 85-94.
464

465 Headlee W, Zalesny R (2019) Allometric relationships for aboveground woody biomass differ among
466 hybrid poplar genomic groups and clones in the North-Central USA. Bioenerg Res 12: 966-976.
467

468 Heppelmann JB, Labelle ER, Wittkopf S, Seeling U (2019) In-stand debarking with the use of modified
469 harvesting heads: a potential solution for key challenges in European forestry. Eur J For
470 Res 138: 1067–1081.
471

472 Hjelm B (2015) Empirical Models for Estimating Volume and Biomass of Poplars on Farmland in
473 Sweden. PhD Thesis, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Faculty of Natural Resources and
474 Agricultural Sciences, Dept. of Crop Production and Ecology. Uppsala, Sweden. 61 p.
475

476 Heilig D, Heil B, Leibing C, Röhle H, Kovács G (2021) Comparison of the Initial Growth of Different
477 Poplar Clones on Four Sites in Western Slovakia—Preliminary Results. Bioenerg Res 14: 374–384.
478

479 Holzleitner F, Kanzian C (2022) Integrated in-stand debarking with a harvester in cut-to-length
480 operations – processing and extraction performance assessment, Int J For Eng 33: 66-79.

481
482 IPP. 2019. Biomass Plantations in Poland.
483 [http://www.internationalpaper.com/company/regions/europe-middle-east-](http://www.internationalpaper.com/company/regions/europe-middle-east-africa/sustainability/highlights/biomass-plantations-in-poland)
484 [africa/sustainability/highlights/biomass-plantations-in-poland](http://www.internationalpaper.com/company/regions/europe-middle-east-africa/sustainability/highlights/biomass-plantations-in-poland). Accessed 08 May 2021
485
486 Kofman PD (2022) Personal communication, E-mail on March 9th, 2022 @ 20:31. Danish Forestry
487 Extension, Vejle, DK.
488
489 Krejza J, Světlík J, Bednář P (2017) Allometric relationship and biomass expansion factors (BEFs)
490 for above- and below-ground biomass prediction and stem volume estimation for ash (*Fraxinus*
491 *excelsior* L.) and oak (*Quercus robur* L.). *Trees* 31: 1303-1316.
492
493 Labelle ER, Soucy M, Cyr A, Pelletier G (2016) Effect of Tree Form on the Productivity of a Cut-to-Length
494 Harvester in a Hardwood Dominated Stand. *Croat J For Eng* 37 (1): 175-183.
495
496 Landgraf D, Carl C, Nuepert M (2020) Biomass yield of 37 Different SRC Poplar Varieties Grown on a
497 Typical Site in North Eastern Germany. *Forests*. 11,1048. 9 p.
498
499 Leonello EC, Gonçalves SP, Fenner PT (2012) Efeito do tempo de experiência de operadores de
500 harvester no rendimento operacional. *Revista Árvore*. 36(6):1129–33.
501
502 Magagnotti N, Kanzian C, Schulmeyer F, Spinelli R (2011) A new guide for work studies in forestry.
503 *Int J For Eng* 24: 249-253.
504
505 Magagnotti N, Spinelli R, Kärhä K, Mederski P (2021) Multi-tree cut-to-length harvesting of short-
506 rotation poplar plantations. *Eur J Forest Res* 140: 345–354.
507
508 McEwan A, Brink M, Spinelli R (2017). Factors affecting the productivity and work quality of chain
509 flail delimiting and debarking. *Silva Fennica* 51: 1599. 14 p.
510
511 McEwan A, Brink M, Spinelli R. (2019) Efficiency of Different Machine Layouts for Chain Flail
512 Delimiting, Debarking and Chipping. *Forests* 10 (2):126.
513
514 McEwan A, Marchi E, Spinelli R, Brink M (2020) Past, present and future of industrial plantation
515 forestry and implication on future timber harvesting technology. *J For Res* 31:339–351.
516
517 Mergl V, Zemánek T, Šušnjar M, Klepárník J (2021) Efficiency of Harvester with the Debarking Head
518 at Logging in Spruce Stands Affected by Bark Beetle Outbreak. *Forests* 12, 1348. 13 p.
519
520 Meyer M, Morgenstern K, Heilig D, Heil B, Kovács G, Leibing C, Krabel D (2021) Biomass Allocation
521 and Root Characteristics of Early-Stage Poplars (*Populus* spp.) for Assessing Their Water-Deficit
522 Response During SRC Establishment. *Bioenerg Res* 14: 385–398.
523
524 Mooney S, Boston K, Greene D (2000) Production and costs of the chambers delimitator in first
525 thinning of pine plantations. *For Prod J* 50: 81-84.
526
527 Nakagawa M, Hamatsu J, Saitou T, Ishida H (2007) Effect of tree size on productivity and time
528 required for work elements in selective thinning by a harvester. *Inter J of For Eng* 18:24–28.

529
530 Okagbue H, Oguntunde P, Obasi E, Akhmetshin E (2021) Trends and usage pattern of SPSS and
531 Minitab software in scientific research. J Phys: Conf Ser 1734 012017. Available on line at:
532 <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1742-6596/1734/1/012017/pdf>. Accessed Oct. 12th,
533 2021.
534
535 Punnett L, Wegman DH (2004). Work-related musculoskeletal disorders: the epidemiologic evidence
536 and the debate. J Electromyogr Kinesiol 14 (1):13–23.
537
538 Raymond KA, Franklin GS (1990) Chain flail delimeter debarkers in eastern Canada: a preliminary
539 assessment. Technical Note TN-153. FERIC. Pointe Claire, QC, 8 p.
540
541 Rubel F, Brugger K, Haslinger K, Auer I (2017) The climate of the European Alps: shift of very high
542 resolution Köppen-Geiger climate zones 1800-2100. Meteorol Z 26:115–125.
543
544 Ruch P, Montagny X, Bouvet A, Ulrich E, George P. 2016. Mechanized processing of big broadleaved
545 crowns: an operational reality. Proceedings of the 49th FORMEC Symposium, September 4th – 7th
546 2016, Warsaw, Poland. P. 111-117.
547
548 Spinelli R, Nati C, Magagnotti N (2005) Harvesting and transport of root biomass from fast-growing
549 poplar plantations. Silva Fennica 39 (4): 539-548.
550
551 Spinelli R, Hartsough BR (2006) Harvesting SRF poplar for pulpwood: Experience in the Pacific
552 Northwest. Biomass Bioenerg 30 (5): 439-445.
553
554 Spinelli R, Visser R (2008) Analyzing and estimating delays in harvester operations. Int J For Eng 19:
555 36–41.
556
557 Spinelli R, Lombardini C, Marchi E, Aminti G (2019) A low-investment technology for the simplified
558 processing of energy wood from coppice forests. Eur J For Res 138 (4): 31-41.
559
560 Spinelli R, Moura de Arruda AC (2019) Productivity and Utilization Benchmarks for Chain Flail
561 Delimeter-Debarkers-Chippers Used in Fast-Growing Plantations. Croat J For Eng 40 (1): 65-80.
562
563 Spinelli R, Mitchell R, Brown M, Magagnotti N, McEwan A (2020a) Manipulating Chain Type and Flail
564 Drum Speed for Better Fibre Recovery in Chain-Flail Delimeter-Debarker-Chipper Operations. Croat
565 J For Eng 41 (1): 137-147.
566
567 Spinelli R, Magagnotti N, Lombardini C (2020b) Low-Investment Fully Mechanized Harvesting of
568 Short-Rotation Poplar (populus spp.) Plantations. Forests 11: 502. 12 p.
569
570 Spinelli R, Magagnotti N, Lombardini C, Mihelic M (2021a) A Low-Investment Option for the
571 Integrated Semi-mechanized Harvesting of Small-Scale, Short-Rotation Poplar Plantations. Small-
572 scale For 20: 59–72.
573
574 Spinelli R, Magagnotti N, Lombardini C, Leonello EC (2021b) Cost-effective Integrated Harvesting of
575 Short-Rotation Poplar Plantations. Bioenerg Res 14: 460–468.
576

577 Spinelli R, De Francesco F, Kovac B, Heger P, Heilig D, Heil B, Kovàcs G, Magagnotti N (2022a) Cut-
578 to-length harvesting options for the integrated harvesting of the European industrial poplar
579 plantations. *Forests* (in press).
580

581 Spinelli R, Kovac B, Heger P, Heilig D, Heil B, Kovàcs G, Magagnotti N (2022b): Manipulating grading
582 strategy for the efficient harvesting of industrial poplar plantations, *Int J For Eng*
583 DOI:10.1080/14942119.2022.2034404
584

585 Spinelli R, Kovac B, Heger P, Heilig D, Heil B, Kovàcs G, Magagnotti N (2022c) The effect of target log
586 length on value recovery and harvesting cost: the example of short rotation poplar plantations.
587 *Forests* 13, 669. 12 p. DOI <https://doi.org/10.3390/f13050669>
588

589 Stokes BJ, Watson WF (1991) Wood recovery with in woods flailing and chipping. *Tappi J* 74(9): 109–
590 113.
591

592 Thompson M, Sturos J (1991). Performance of a portable chain flail delimeter/debarker processing
593 Northern hardwoods. Research paper NC 297. USDA Forest Service, North Central Forest
594 Experimental Station, St. Paul, MN.
595

596 Urban J, Čermák J, Ceulemans R (2015) Above- and below-ground biomass, surface and volume,
597 and stored water in a mature Scots pine stand. *Eur J For Res* 134: 61-74.
598

599 Verlinden MS, Broeckx LS, Van den Bulcke J, Van Acker J, Ceulemans R (2013) Comparative study of
600 biomass determinants of 12 poplar (*Populus*) genotypes in a high-density short-rotation culture. *For*
601 *Ecol Manag* 307: 101-111.
602

603 Watson W, Twaddle A, Hudson B (1993) Review of chain flail delimiting-debarking. *J For Eng* 4: 37-
604 52.
605

606 Werner C, Haas E, Grote R, Gauder M, Graeff-Hönninger S, Claupein W, Butterbach-Bahl K (2012)
607 Biomass production potential from *Populus* short rotation systems in Romania. *GCB Bioenerg* 4:
608 642–653.
609
610
611
612
613
614
615
616
617
618
619
620
621
622
623
624

625
626
627
628
629
630
631
632
633

Table 1 – Characteristics of the test tree piles

Piles		Strong	Weak	MW
Observations	n°	8	8	p-Value
Mass	BDT	3.73	2.72	0.0018
Trees	n°	134	119	0.0176
DBH	cm	12.4	10.9	0.0070
Height	m	14.7	14.3	0.0060
Mass	kg DM	28	23	0.0176
Stocking	Trees ha ⁻¹	1725	1661	0.3446
Stocking	BDT ha ⁻¹	47.9	37.3	0.0008

634 Notes: Median values; BDT = Bone-Dry tons (0% water mass fraction);
635 DBH = Diameter at breast height; DM = dry matter; MW = Mann-Whitney
636 non-parametric test for unpaired comparison (two levels).
637
638
639

640
641
642
643
644
645
646

Table 2 – Chainflail productivity and log yield as derived from the pile-level study

Piles		Strong	Weak	MW
Observations	n°	8	8	p-Value
Logs	BDT	2.57	1.14	0.0008
Chips	BDT	1.16	1.58	0.0742
Log yield	%	68.8	41.9	0.0008
Time	SMH	1.34	0.62	0.0008
Productivity	Trees SMH ⁻¹	103	193	0.0008
Productivity	BDT SMH ⁻¹	2.88	4.13	0.0008

647 Notes: Median values; BDT = Bone-Dry tons (0% water mass fraction);
648 Log yield % = 100 * log mass/total mass; SMH = Scheduled Machine
649 Hour, including delays (here estimated at 20% of the net work time);
650 MW = Mann-Whitney non-parametric test for unpaired comparison
651 (two levels).
652
653
654

655
656
657
658
659
660
661
662
663
664

Table 3 – Results of the cycle-level study

		Strong	Weak	MW
Observations	n°	8	8	p-Value
Cycles observation ⁻¹	n°	16	15	
Trees cycle ⁻¹	n°	4.9	6.4	0.0127
Logs tree ⁻¹	n°	1.5	0.9	0.0034
Cycle time	s	130	106	0.0281
Work pace	Cycles PMH ⁻¹	28	34	0.0281
Productivity	Trees PMH ⁻¹	137	218	0.0034

665 Notes: Median values; PMH = Productive Machine Hour, excluding delays; MW =
666 Mann-Whitney non-parametric test for unpaired comparison (two levels).

667
668
669
670
671
672
673
674
675
676
677
678

Table 4 – Productivity of CFDD used in hardwood tree farms: summary of bibliographic information

Make	Model	Chipper	Species	Piece size, t	t SMH ⁻¹	Utilization %	Country	Re
Peterson Pacific	DDC 5000	Yes	Populus sp	0.131	52	89	USA	Sp
Morbark	2455	Yes	Populus sp	0.143	48	89	USA	Sp
Peterson Pacific	DDC 5000	Yes	Populus sp	0.180-0.200	49	95	USA	Ha
Peterson Pacific	DDC 5000	Yes	Eucalyptus sp.	-	38	45	Brazil	Sp
Peterson Pacific	DDC5000	Yes	E. globulus	0.105-0.344	27	57	Australia	M
Husky Precision	FD 4300	Yes	E. globulus	0.105-0.344	23	56	Australia	M
Morbark	2455	No	E. globulus	0.204	59	20	Chile	M
Peterson Pacific	DDC 5000	Yes	E. globulus	0.010	40-45	20	Australia	Sp
Husky Precision	FD 2300	Yes	E. globulus	0.200	53	92	Australia	GH
Peterson Pacific	DDC 5000	Yes	Eucalyptus sp.	0.134	26	77	USA	Sp
Morbark	2348	Yes	Eucalyptus sp.	0.086	34	75	USA	Sp

Notes: Chipper = if Yes the CFDD is integrated with the chipper, if No it is not; SMH = Scheduled Machine Hour, including delays; Utilization = Productive hours/Scheduled hours

Table 5 – Log yield obtained from the harvesting of SRP plantations

Case n°	Place	Method	Equipment	DBH	kg tree ⁻¹	SED	Log Yield	
1	Malacky (SK)	WTH	Chain flail	11	51	7	42	<i>This study</i>
2	Malacky (SK)	WTH	Chain flail	12	62	7	69	<i>This study</i>
3	Kwydzyn (PL)	CTL	Harvester	12	56	7	37-42	Magagnotti et al. 2020
4	Malacky (SK)	CTL	Harvester	12	58-70	7-8	50-61	Spinelli et al 2022b
5	Malacky (SK)	CTL	Harvester	12	65-75	8	52-60	Spinelli et al. 2022c (in p
6	Malacky (SK)	CTL	Harvester	10	29	7	26	Spinelli et al. 2022a (in p
7	Malacky (SK)	CTL	Harvester	12	62	7	62	Spinelli et al. 2022a (in p
8	Cossato (I)	WTH	Grapple-saw	15	103	7	80*	Spinelli et al. 2020b
9	Sezzadio (I)	WTH	Grapple-saw	15	95	7	41	Spinelli et al 2021a
10	Skalica (SK)	WTH	Grapple-saw	12	51	7	51**	Spinelli et al 2021b

Notes: DBH = Diameter at Breast Height; SED = Small-End Diameter; Log yield = 100 * Log mass/Total mass; CTL = Cut-to-Length; WTH = Whole-Tree

Harvesting; * eventually reduced to 40% due to high rejection rate; ** poor delimiting quality; In all cases, trees were processed into 4-m long logs

Figure 1 – A schematic drawing of the prototype CFDD

Figure 2 – The machine at work in Western Slovakia

Figure 3 – The two chain drums adapted for horizontal feeding

Figure 4 – Delimiting quality obtained with a cut-to-length processor (above) and the prototype CFDD (below)

Figure 5 – Results of the elemental time study

